

Appendix

Listing A: An excerpt of the test log .txt file

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Test Case Number:220
Test Data: , VibrationLevel-39.06615213197612, GPSConn- 0.7178025202465592, WindSpeed-
23.54547198891945, rcConn- 0.9052348267942126, Lat1- -35.36592348852166, lon1- 149.16512000232973,
Lat2- -35.36393776175138, lon2- 149.16436420243542, Lat3- -35.365890831167384, lon3-
149.16751046078397, Lat4- -35.36274058417619, lon4- 149.1676834751607, Lat5- -35.361662079803885,
lon5- 149.16684492041168, Lat6- -35.36186442026782, lon6- 149.16780817228164, Lat7-
-35.36131400560128, lon7- 149.16369058023716, Lat8- -35.363420256062966, lon8- 149.16773709401895
—leader should be in waiting state if any of the vehicles have dist > 3
Runtime Observed Data: currentDistanceToWaypoint: 33, waypointReached: 0, currentGroundSpeed:
0.0163411907851696, currentAirSpeed: 0.004000000189989805, currentAltitude: 50, seconddist: 38,
-Constraints Failed:
-Category Constraints Failed Count:0
+Constraints Passed:UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.armed=true)->size()->size()->3 and
UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>5 and
a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size()->size()->3 and UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or
a.mode='AUTO')->size()->size()->3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and
a.id=1)->size()->size()->1 and
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and
n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size()->size()->1 implies
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=0 and
a.id=1)->size()->size()->1!@!
+Category Constraints Passed Count:1
—leader should be in waiting state =With Wind= if any of the vehicles have dist > 3
Runtime Observed Data: currentDistanceToWaypoint: 50, waypointReached: 0, currentGroundSpeed:
1.4489208459854126, currentAirSpeed: 0.9130000472068787, currentAltitude: 50, windSpeed:
23.54547119140625, diff: 332.0, seconddist: 60,
-Constraints Failed:
-Category Constraints Failed Count:0
+Constraints Passed:UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.armed=true)->size()->size()->3 and
UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>5 and
a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size()->size()->3 and UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or
a.mode='AUTO')->size()->size()->3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and
a.id=1)->size()->size()->1 and
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.environment.windSpeed>=20 and
n.environment.windSpeed<50 and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and
n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size()->size()->1 implies
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=0 and
a.id=1)->size()->size()->1!@!
+Category Constraints Passed Count:1
—leader should be in waiting state =With Vibration= if any of the vehicles have dist > 3
Runtime Observed Data: currentDistanceToWaypoint: 50, waypointReached: 0, currentGroundSpeed:
0.01949155144393444, currentAirSpeed: 0.003000000026077032, currentAltitude: 50,
currentVibrationLevel: 39.0661506652832, seconddist: 60,
-Constraints Failed:
-Category Constraints Failed Count:0
+Constraints Passed:UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.armed=true)->size()->size()->3 and
UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>5 and
a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size()->size()->3 and UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or
a.mode='AUTO')->size()->size()->3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and
a.id=1)->size()->size()->1 and
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.currentVibrationLevel>=20 and
n.currentVibrationLevel<40 and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and
n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size()->size()->1 implies
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=0 and
a.id=1)->size()->size()->1!@!
+Category Constraints Passed Count:1
—leader should be in waiting state =With Wind and Vib= if any of the vehicles have dist > 3
```

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Runtime Observed Data: currentDistanceToWaypoint: 10, waypointReached: 0, currentGroundSpeed:
  1.025519609451294, currentAirSpeed: 0.4570000171661377, currentAltitude: 50, windSpeed:
  23.54547119140625, currentVibrationLevel: 39.0661506652832, diff: 334.0, seconddist: 20,
-Constraints Failed:
-Category Constraints Failed Count:0
+Constraints Passed:UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.armed=true)->size ()=3 and
  UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>5 and
    a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or
    a.mode='AUTO')->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and
    a.id=1)->size ()=1 and
  UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.environment.windSpeed>=20 and
    n.environment.windSpeed<50 or n.currentVibrationLevel>=20 and n.currentVibrationLevel<40 and
    n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size ()=1
  implies UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=0
  and a.id=1)->size ()=1!@!
+Category Constraints Passed Count:1
—leader should be in waiting state =With RC fail= if any of the vehicles have dist > 3
Runtime Observed Data: currentDistanceToWaypoint: 23, waypointReached: 0, currentGroundSpeed:
  0.01965656876564026, currentAirSpeed: 0.003000000026077032, currentAltitude: 50, RCConnected: 1.0,
  seconddist: 10,
-Constraints Failed:
-Category Constraints Failed Count:0
+Constraints Passed:UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.armed=true)->size ()=3 and
  UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>5 and
    a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or
    a.mode='AUTO')->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and
    a.id=1)->size ()=1 and
  UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.connection.RCConnected=false and
    n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size ()=1
  implies UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=0
  and a.id=1)->size ()=1!@!
+Category Constraints Passed Count:1
—leader should be in waiting state =With GPS fail= if any of the vehicles have dist > 3
Runtime Observed Data: currentDistanceToWaypoint: 50, waypointReached: 0, currentGroundSpeed:
  0.020097658038139343, currentAirSpeed: 0.0020000000949949026, currentAltitude: 50, GPSConnected:
  1.0, seconddist: 55,
-Constraints Failed:
-Category Constraints Failed Count:0
+Constraints Passed:UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.armed=true)->size ()=3 and
  UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>5 and
    a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or
    a.mode='AUTO')->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and
    a.id=1)->size ()=1 and
  UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.connection.GPSConnected=false and
    n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size ()=1
  implies UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=0
  and a.id=1)->size ()=1!@!
+Category Constraints Passed Count:1
—Self-adaptation in case of GPS Disconn on Flying
Runtime Observed Data: GPSConnected: 1.0, mode: 2,
-Constraints Failed:UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.armed=true)->size ()=3 and
  UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>5 and
    a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->forAll(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or
    a.mode='AUTO')->size ()=3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and
    a.id=1)->size ()=1 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.connection.GPSConnected=false and
    a.id=1)->size ()=1 implies UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mode='RTL' and a.id=1)->size ()=1!@!
= Behavior Failed: Self-adaptation in case of GPS Disconn on Flying
-Category Constraints Failed Count:1
+Constraints Passed:
+Category Constraints Passed Count:0
Total Failed count: 1
Total Passed count: 6
Total Constraints Evaluated: 7
Test case Result:Failed

```



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UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and a.id=1)->size()-1 and
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and
n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size()-1 and
UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=0 and a.id=1
and a.RCCConnected=false)->size()-1 implies UAV.allInstances()->exists(n|n.mode='RTL' and
n.id=1)->size()-1

```


Figure A: UAS-SM (S) path for UAS-AR

Listing C: Adaptation Rule

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1 UAV.allInstances()->forall(a|a.armed=true)->size()-3 and UAV.allInstances()->forall(a|a.altitude.
currentAltitude>5 and a.altitude.currentAltitude<10 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed>2 and a.speed.
currentGroundSpeed<=10)->size()-3 and UAV.allInstances()->forall(a|a.mode='GUIDED' or a.mode='AUTO')
)->size()-3 and UAV.allInstances()->forall(a|a.altitude.currentAltitude>10 and a.altitude.
currentAltitude<100 and a.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<360)->size()-3 and UAV.allInstances()->
exists(a|a.mission.waypointReached=true and a.id=1)->size()-1 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.
neighbor->exists(n|n.currentVibrationLevel>=20 and n.currentVibrationLevel<=40 and n.mission.
currentDistanceToWaypoint>3 and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size()-1 implies UAV.
allInstances()->exists(a|a.speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=50 and a.id=1)->
size()-1

```

Listing D: Adaptation Rule - Transformed

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1 UAV.allInstances()->forall(a|a.armed=true)->size()-3 and UAV.allInstances()->forall(a|a.altitude.
currentAltitude>5 and a.altitude.currentAltitude<100)->size()-3 and UAV.allInstances()->forall(a|a.
mode='GUIDED' or a.mode='AUTO'))->size()-3 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.mission.
waypointReached=true and a.id=1)->size()-1 and UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.neighbor->exists(n|n.
currentVibrationLevel>=20 and n.currentVibrationLevel<40 and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint>3
and n.mission.currentDistanceToWaypoint<=500))->size()-1 implies UAV.allInstances()->exists(a|a.
speed.currentAirSpeed=0 and a.speed.currentGroundSpeed=50 and a.id=1)->size()-1

```

Algorithm A Test Case Generation

1: **Input:** N : Number of Variables, $ListVarLL$: Variable Lower Limits, $ListVarUL$: Variable Upper Limits
2: **Output:** $OptTestCases$: Population containing an optimal set of test cases
3: **Begin**
4: **Initialize:** P : Population of individuals, ind : An individual in P , $stoppingCriterion$: the stopping criterion set for GA
5: $P \leftarrow initializePopulation(ListVarLL, ListVarUL, N)$
6: **while** not $stoppingCriterion$ **do**
7: $P_{up} \leftarrow PerformCrossoverAndMutation(P)$
8: $P \leftarrow P \cup P_{up}$
9: **for** $ind \in P$
10: $calculateFitness(ind)$ \triangleright this function sends the ind to the test case execution module, test cases are executed, then they are evaluated to calculate the fitness of the ind
11: $P \leftarrow SelectInd\ with\ better\ fitness$
12: $OptTestCases \leftarrow P$

Algorithm B Test Case Execution

1: **Input:** $stoppingCriterion$: stopping criterion set in test case generator, $config$: UAS Simulator Configuration
2: **Output:** $ResFile$: Test Case Execution Result File
3: **Begin**
4: **Initialize:** n : holds counter for test case generator evaluations, $list$: a list that gets an individual from genetic algorithm as a test case, $observationlist$: a list of run time variable values related to the UAS, $totalDist$: holds the total branch distance calculated for all constraints evaluated, res : a list that holds the result of test case evaluation, failed constraints, passed constraints, $paramVal$: a list that holds the values of parameters in the $observationlist$, $geneVal$: a list that holds the gene values or test case values in $list$, $finalFitness$: holds the of fitness calculated for a test case, BD : gets normalized sum of branch distances calculated for a constraint evaluated, $MaxBD$: gets maximum BD value among all constraints evaluated
5: $configureSimulator(config)$
6: **while** not $stoppingCriterion$ **do**
7: $list \leftarrow getTestCase()$ \triangleright get ind from test case generator
8: $startSimulator()$
9: Connect UAV(s)
10: $setVariableValues(list)$
11: $observationlist \leftarrow getUASStatus()$
12: **if** $paramVal \in observationlist == geneVal \in list$
13: $res, totalDist \leftarrow evaluateTestCase(action, state, observationlist)$
14: $BD \leftarrow calculateBD(totalDist)$
15: $MaxBD \leftarrow calculateMaxBD(BD)$
16: $finalFitness \leftarrow calculatefitness(MaxBD, res, observationlist)$
17: $sendcalculatedfitness(finalFitness)$ \triangleright this function sends individual fitness value to the Test Case Generator
18: $ResFile \leftarrow res$
19: **return** $ResFile$

Algorithm C Test Case Evaluation

1: **Input:** CD : $UAS-CD(S)$, $observationlist$: a list of run-time variable values related to the UAS, $consList$: $UAS-AR$
2: **Output:** $reslist$: a list that has the number of failed constraints, number of passed constraints, list of passed constraints, list of failed constraints, $totalDist$: holds the total branch distance calculated for all constraints evaluated
3: **Begin**
4: **Initialize:** $cons$: a string that holds the selected constraint, $attrValuesC$: a list that holds the attribute values of the constraint evaluated, $attrValuesL$: a list that holds the attribute values corresponding to the evaluated constraint selected from the $observationList$, res : the result of the evaluation, $dist$: branch distance calculated for test case through constraint evaluation
5: $stateCons \leftarrow getconstraints(consList)$
6: $ins \leftarrow getCDInstance(UAS-CD(S))$
7: **for** $cons \in stateCons$
8: $res \leftarrow evaluate(ins, cons, observationlist)$
9: $dist \leftarrow getDistance(attrValuesC \in cons, attrValuesL \in observationlist)$
10: $totalDist \leftarrow totalDist + dist$
11: $reslist \leftarrow res, cons$
12: **return** $reslist, totalDist$
